

PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS OF DEVELOPMENT OF COTTON CLUSTERS IN UZBEKISTAN: ECONOMIC, SOCIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL ASPECTS

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The cotton industry of Uzbekistan is one of the key sectors of the country's economy, providing a significant contribution to GDP, exports and employment. Since 2017, the government of Uzbekistan has made significant efforts to reform the cotton industry, introducing a cluster system as one of the main mechanisms for increasing productivity and modernizing the sector. However, despite a number of positive changes, cotton clusters face a number of problems that limit their efficiency and sustainability.

Key words: Cotton clusters, agriculture, reforms, water resources, financing, technological modernization, labor rights, ecology, sustainable development.

Introduction.

Before the reforms, the cotton industry of Uzbekistan was characterized by a centralized management system, where the state played a leading role in the production, processing and export of cotton. This structure led to a number of problems related to inefficient resource management, low productivity and low incomes of farmers [1]. In 2017, the government launched a reform, the main element of which was the creation of cotton clusters - associations of agricultural producers, processing and exporting enterprises operating in one system. This initiative is aimed at increasing the efficiency of resource use and creating added value at all stages of production.

Key challenges of cotton clusters.

1. Insufficient financing and access to credit

One of the key challenges faced by cotton clusters is limited access to financing. Farmers and small businesses in clusters often have difficulty obtaining loans due to high interest rates and lack of liquidity. Although the government has taken steps to improve financial support for the sector, including through interest rate subsidies on loans, this process remains ineffective, especially for small and medium farmers [2].

2. Uneven income distribution

Despite the integration of all participants in the production chain within clusters, the problem of uneven income distribution remains relevant. Farmers, who are the main producers of raw materials, often receive a smaller share of income compared to processing and exporting companies. This leads to a decrease in farmers' motivation to improve product quality and introduce innovations.

3. Technological Lagging

Although the creation of cotton clusters involves the introduction of modern technologies, in reality many farmers continue to use outdated production methods. This is due to the insufficient level of education and training of personnel in rural areas, as well as the lack of financial resources to purchase modern equipment and machinery. As a result, labor productivity remains low, and the quality of products does not always meet international standards [3].

4. Water Resources

The problem of rational use of water resources is critical for the cotton industry in Uzbekistan, where a significant part of the territory is arid. Cotton is a crop that requires a large amount of water, and the existing irrigation system is often characterized by low efficiency and large water losses. In the context of increasing competition for water resources in Central Asia, this problem can become a serious constraint on further cluster development.

5. Social and Labor Issues

One of the most sensitive issues remains the observance of labor rights and social responsibility. In the past, Uzbekistan has faced international criticism over the use of forced labor in the cotton industry. Despite significant progress in eradicating the problem, cases of labour exploitation still exist, particularly during the harvest season. The lack of effective control mechanisms and inadequate protection of workers' rights remain problematic aspects of the cluster system.

6. Environmental Challenges

Increasing the scale of cotton production without due attention to environmental aspects leads to land degradation and environmental pollution. The negative impact on soil and water resources is aggravated by the use of pesticides and chemical fertilizers, which negatively affects the ecosystem of the regions where cotton clusters are concentrated. The introduction of sustainable production methods and improved environmental monitoring remain urgent tasks [4].

Solutions.

To solve the existing problems of cotton clusters, an integrated approach is needed, including both government support measures and private initiatives.

- Financial support: It is necessary to improve access to credit and financing, especially for small farmers. This can be achieved through the creation of specialized lending programs with preferential terms.

- Improving the efficiency of income distribution: Introducing mechanisms for fair distribution of income between all participants in the production chain.

- Technological modernization: To improve productivity and product quality, it is necessary to develop educational programs for farmers and stimulate the introduction of modern technologies through subsidies and preferential terms.

- Sustainable use of resources: The introduction of modern irrigation systems and precision farming technologies can significantly reduce water losses and improve resource efficiency [5].

- Social responsibility: Further development of labor control measures and ensuring respect for workers' rights is an important step.

- Environmental sustainability: The introduction of stricter environmental monitoring standards and the introduction of organic farming methods will help reduce the negative impact on the environment.

Conclusion.

Cotton clusters in Uzbekistan play an important role in the country's economy and provide employment for a significant part of the population. However, to achieve their full potential, a number of key issues need to be addressed, such as insufficient funding, technological lag and uneven income distribution. Comprehensive reforms aimed at eliminating these issues can contribute to the sustainable development of the cotton industry and improve the living conditions of the rural population.

References:

1. Bekmirzaev, A. Sh. (2020). Problems of reforming the cotton industry of Uzbekistan. *Journal of Agrarian Economics*, 12(3), 45-58.
2. Saidov, I. H. (2019). Cotton clusters as a new stage in the development of the agricultural sector of Uzbekistan. Tashkent: Publishing House of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan.

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3. FAO (2021). Sustainable use of water resources in cotton growing in Central Asia: challenges and prospects. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.
4. Mirsaidov, N. A. (2021). Problems of technological modernization of cotton clusters in Uzbekistan. Bulletin of Agricultural Research, 7(2), 30-38.
5. Khalmatov, U. T. (2022). Social and labor aspects in the cotton sector of Uzbekistan: history and modern challenges. Economics and management in the agricultural sector, 5(4), 75-89.